

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319537046>

Germanium–Silicon Based Hetero Junction Cylindrical Gate All Around Field Effect Transistor for Improved Performance

Article · September 2017

CITATIONS

0

READS

200

4 authors:

Sakib Quader

Shanghai Jiao Tong University

5 PUBLICATIONS 3 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Abu Bakar Siddik

Kyung Hee University

5 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

N M Mahmud Hossain

United International University

4 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Iqbal Bahar Chowdhury

United International University

58 PUBLICATIONS 82 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Gate -All-Around FET [View project](#)

Graphene Nanoribbon Based FinFET [View project](#)

Germanium-Silicon Based Hetero Junction Cylindrical Gate All Around Field Effect Transistor for Improved Performance

Sakib Quader

United International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abu Bakar Siddik

United International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

N. M. Mahmud Hossain

United International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Md. Iqbal Bahar Chowdhury

United International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

Performance analysis of a hetero junction cylindrical gate all around field effect transistor (HJ-CGAA FET) is reported in this paper where source-drain material is germanium (Ge) and silicon (Si) is used as channel material. We also replaced the traditional silicon-di-oxide (SiO_2) layer with silicon nitride (Si_3N_4). The simulation results indicate that this hetero junction structure is able to provide an improved performance over a conventional cylindrical gate all around FET. An optimized DIBL of 75.5167 mV/V and SS of 68.2 mV/dec is achieved for 10nm technology node from TCAD simulation. Other performance parameters are also calculated which anticipates that this FET can be scaled down up to 5nm while maintaining a better On-Off current ratio.

Keywords

hetero junction cylindrical gate all around FET, scaling, drain induced barrier lowering, subthreshold swing, silicon nitride

INTRODUCTION

In order to integrate more numbers of transistor in a single chip, field effect transistors (FET) are required to downscale invasively. However, downscaling the conventional planner FET has become a major challenge to device engineers as shorter channel FETs has some serious issues like short channel effects (SCEs), degraded subthreshold swing (SS), higher Off current (I_{off}) [1-3]. Among these SCEs drain induced barrier lowering (DIBL) affects the I_{off} and SS by a large amount which needs to be optimized as much as possible. Many techniques to solve these problems of shorter channel FETs has been introduced over the decades like changing the FET structure, introducing new channel-source-drain materials, High-K dielectrics as oxide layer etc. [4]. However, gate all around FET provides the highest electrostatic control over the flow of the current and manages to scale down the FET further compared to double-gate, tri-gate, quadruple-gate, omega-gate, pi-gate FETs [13,14]. In addition, indium arsenide (InAs), germanium (Ge), gallium nitride (GaN), gallium arsenide (GaAs) and graphene can be the alternative materials to silicon (Si) for manufacturing the field effect transistors [5-8]. This work focuses on hetero junction cylindrical gate all around (HJ-CGAA)FET having Silicon and Germanium as channel and source-drain (S-D) materials respectively. Silicon Nitride (Si_3N_4) is used as the oxide material in this HJ-CGAA FET which ensures large coupling capacitance, high chemical stability over silicon-di-oxide (SiO_2) and high melting point [9]. Thus, a strong electric field is produced and uniformly distributed over the channel which confirms excellent gate control over the flow of current. Pure Ge delivers more than 2x mobility for electrons compared to Si [12] which is why Ge is preferred as S-D over Si. Silicon has intrinsic carrier concentration (ICC) of $1.45 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ [10] which is much lower than the ICC of Ge $2.4 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ [10]. Because of this lower intrinsic carrier concentration Si provides lower off state current. If we combine all of these advantages together we may expect, lower I_{off} , higher On-Off current ratio, better

SS and an optimized DIBL effect after this modification. Our simulation results also reveal that an improved performance up to 5nm technology node can be achieved with HJ-CGAA FET.

DEVICE STRUCTURE AND SIMULATION

3D HJ-CGAA FET is demonstrated in **fig.1** where 1(a) shows the 3D full view and 1(b) shows the quarter view of the device.

Fig1: (a) 3D full view of the HJ-CGAA-FET (b) quarter view of the device

The device has Ge source and drain of uniform doping of $1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and Si channel has a doping concentration of $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. A metal gate of work function 5eV is used to encircle the silicon nanowire channel along with a 1nm thickness of Si_3N_4 oxide layer. The device has a channel thickness of 5nm along diameter. The simulations were conducted using ATLAS tool of Silvaco TCAD software by taking an ultra-thin 2D slice from the 3D structure shown in **fig. 2**.

Fig2:2D slice along diameter

First Schrodinger equation was solved to determine the eigenfunction and eigenvalues at each slice and then non-equilibrium Greens function (NEGF) was solved using mode-space approach to determine the quantum transport of the device. Three different node sizes of 10nm, 7nm and 5nm was studied to analyze the performance of the FET.

SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Transfer characteristics and other performance parameters generated from ATLAS Silvaco TCAD simulation are demonstrated and discussed in this section. Transfer characteristics of 10nm HJ-CGAA FET for two different drain voltage (V_D) is shown in **fig.3** which clearly reveals that not only off-state current is extremely low but the device also has a higher on state current. The linear region slope is sharp enough that determines an excellent On-Off current ratio and SS as well. The curve also explains that the I_{off} of 10nm HJ-CGAA is less sensitive to V_D . Good electrostatic control over the channel, lower ICC of Si during no bias condition and novel electron transport capability of Ge S-D are the key reasons behind this enhanced transfer characteristics.

Fig 3: Transfer characteristics of 10nm JL-DCGAA-FET

Fig.4 and **fig.5** demonstrates the transfer characteristics of the HJ-CGAA FET of node size 7nm and 5nm respectively. In case of 5nm and 7nm node the On-Off current ratios are in acceptable range. The high-k dielectric Si_3N_4 creates a large coupling capacitance which results a well distributed strong electric field over the channel. Thus, number of transport carriers change dramatically when gate bias is applied which is why a sharp linear region slope is achieved. Though 7nm and 5nm node size shows off state current that is not immune to increase in V_D , but it still allows the FET to scale below 10nm.

Fig 4: Transfer characteristics of 7nm JL-DCGAA-FET

Fig 5: Transfer characteristics of 10nm JL-DCGAA-FET

Table 1 shows the performance parameters of the 10nm node where we can see that a SS of 68.2 mV/dec can be accomplished by 10nm HJ-CGAA FET which is better than 10nm GAA performed by P Zheng et. al [11]. The DIBL problem is greatly optimized in this structure. Only a DIBL of 75.5167 mv/V is obtained from a 10nm HJ-CGAA FET. To verify the claim of this optimized DIBL, the band diagrams of 10nm HJ-CGAA FET for zero gate biasing condition across source-channel-drain region is shown in **fig.6** and **fig.7**. These two figures demonstrate the conduction band energy for two different drain voltages 0.05V and 0.8V respectively. It is clear from **fig.6** and **fig.7** that the barrier height at source end decreases negligibly for increasing the drain voltage which is why HJ-CGAA FET manages to suppress the DIBL by a large amount.

Fig6: Energy band diagram of 10nm JL-CGAA FET for $V_D=0.05V$

Fig7: Energy band diagram of 10nm JL-CGAA FET for $V_D=0.05V$

An impressive SS, on current, off current and on-off current ratio is reported in **table 2&3** for 7 and 5nm node size respectively. Only 0.7V is required as gate bias to attain an I_{ON} of 2.96 μA from a 5nm technology node that elicits HJ-CGAA FET can be a solution to minimize the static power for shorter channel FET as the supply voltage is extremely in low range. The on-off current ratio for 7nm HJ-CGAA FET is greater than 10^8 that explains the reason of getting an improved SS of 85.1mV/dec. The device manages a higher on-off current ratio ($>10^4$) for even 5nm node size which proves the scalability and possibility of the device for shorter channel length.

Parameters	Process		
	10nm	7nm	5nm
I_{ON} (A)	1.68E-06	2.76E-06	1.06E-06
I_{OFF} (A)	1.69E-18	9.24E-15	1.87E-11
I_{ON} / I_{OFF}	9.94E+11	2.99E+08	5.67E+04
SS (mV/dec)	68.2	85.1	113.8
DIBL (mV/V)	75.5167	104.367	283.997

Table 1. Performance parameters for 10, 7 and 5nm JL-CGAA FET for $V_D= 0.05V$

Parameters	Process		
	10nm	7nm	5nm
I_{ON} (A)	3.35E-06	3.60E-06	2.96E-06
I_{OFF} (A)	9.55E-18	2.56E-13	3.31E-10
I_{ON} / I_{OFF}	3.51E+11	1.41E+07	8.94E+03
SS (mV/dec)	70.4	89.5	122.6

Table 2: Performance parameters for 10, 7 and 5nm JL-CGAA FET for $V_D= 0.8V$

CONCLUSION

A Ge-Si based hetero junction cylindrical gate all around FET having Si_3N_4 as oxide is studied in this work. To investigate the performance of this FET, ATLAS Silvaco TCAD simulation was conducted for three different node sizes 10, 7 and 5nm. The device shows an improved performance in terms of On-off current ratio, SS and DIBL over conventional cylindrical gate all around FET. The deterioration of its performance parameters with the decrease of the node size is in an acceptable limit which makes this FET superior compared to single, multi-gate and gate all around homojunction devices.

REFERENCES

- [1] D'Agostino F, Quercia D. Short-channel effects in MOSFETs. Introduction to VLSI design (EECS 467). 2000 Dec.
- [2] Frank DJ, Dennard RH, Nowak E, Solomon PM, Taur Y, Wong HS. Device scaling limits of Si MOSFETs and their application dependencies. Proceedings of the IEEE. 2001 Mar;89(3):259-88.
- [3] Kashizadeh A, Sharifi MJ. NEGF analysis of current oscillation in Germanium nanowire MOSFETs. In Electrical Engineering (ICEE), 2014 22nd Iranian Conference on 2014 May 20 (pp. 242-246). IEEE.
- [4] Skotnicki T, Hutchby JA, King TJ, Wong HS, Boeuf F. The end of CMOS scaling: toward the introduction of new materials and structural changes to improve MOSFET performance. IEEE Circuits and Devices Magazine. 2005 Jan;21(1):16-26.
- [5] Schwierz F. Graphene transistors. Nature nanotechnology. 2010 Jul 1;5(7):487-96.
- [6] Nguyen C, Micovic M, Wong D, Kurdoghlian A, Hashimoto P, Janke P, McCray L, Moon J. GaN HFET technology for RF applications. In GaAs IC Symposium, 2000. 22nd Annual 2000 Nov 5 (pp. 11-14). IEEE.
- [7] Zhang C, Li X. III-V nanowire transistors for low-power logic applications: A review and outlook. IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices. 2016 Jan;63(1):223-34.
- [8] Hsueh CL. Alternative materials for next-generation transistors: High-k/germanium-based MOSFET. Rutgers The State University of New Jersey-New Brunswick; 2008.
- [9] Chaudhary R, Sharma A, Sinha S, Yadav J, Sharma R, Mukhiya R, Khanna VK. Fabrication and characterization of Al gate n-MOSFET, on-chip fabricated with Si_3N_4 ISFET. In VLSI Design and Test (VDATE), 2015 19th International Symposium on 2015 Jun 26 (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [10] Semiconductor V. General Properties of Si, Ge, SiGe, SiO_2 and Si_3N_4 . accessed Last Accessed: March. 2012;10:2012.
- [11] Zheng P, Liao YB, Damrongplisit N, Chiang MH, Liu TJ. Variation-Aware Comparative Study of 10-nm GAA Versus FinFET 6-T SRAM Performance and Yield. IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices. 2014 Dec;61(12):3949-54.
- [12] Shang H, Okorn-Schmidt H, Chan KK, Copel M, Ott JA, Kozlowski PM, Steen SE, Cordes SA, Wong HS, Jones EC, Haensch WE. High mobility p-channel germanium MOSFETs with a thin Ge oxynitride gate dielectric. In Electron Devices Meeting, 2002. IEDM'02. International 2002 Dec 8 (pp. 441-444). IEEE.
- [13] Sharma A, Akashe S. Performance Analysis of Gate-All-Around Field Effect Transistor for CMOS Nanoscale Devices. International Journal of Computer Applications. 2013 Jan 1;84(10).
- [14] Lu W, Xie P, Lieber CM. Nanowire transistor performance limits and applications. IEEE transactions on Electron Devices. 2008 Nov;55(11):2859-76.